

Life style of Transgender/Gay in Modern Society

1.Dr. Syed Mahaboob Basha

Assistant Professor

Department of English

YSREC of Yogi Vemana University Proddatur

2.Dr. B.R.Lakshmi

Assistant Professor

Department of English

G. Narayanamma Institute of Science & Technology,

Sheikpet, HYD

3.Dr.P.Kousar Basha

Assistant Professor

Department of English

RGM CET, Nandyal

4.Dr.Imran Mahammad

Associate Professor

QIS College of Engineering and Technology, Ongole

5.Mr.K.Eswar Reddy

Assistant Professor of English

Aditya College of Engineering(Autonomus) Madanapalli

Abstract:

Gender expression is a term used to describe people's outward presentation of their gender. Transgender is an umbrella term for persons whose gender identity or expression (masculine, feminine, other) is different from their sex (male, female) at birth. Gender identity refers to one's internal understanding of one's own gender, or the gender with which a person identifies. In South Asia gender expansive identities have historically been present in the subcontinent, the well being transgender/gay/hijra/third gender people of historical, spiritual and cultural significance in South Asian Society. Hijra and individuals of diverse gender identities have documented in religious and cultural text and legends. These individuals often form international communities for community as well as survival.

Key Words: Gender, Identity, Cultural Significance, Discrimination, Rights...etc

Introduction:

Most historians agree that there is evidence of homosexual activity and same-sex love, whether such relationships were accepted or persecuted, in every documented culture. We know that homosexuality existed in ancient and it is prohibited in all the religious books, whereas it flourished between both men and women. Here's a look at their history, from

ancient civilizations to the modern rights movement. The term “transgender” wasn’t coined until the 1960s—but people have always challenged the gender binary.

History of Transgender/Gay:

Everyone has a gender identity and a sexual orientation, but a person’s gender does not determine a person’s sexual orientation. Gender identity and sexual orientation are different facets of identity. Susan Stryker Gender theorist defined that transgender as encompassing "all identities or practices that cross over, cut across, move between, or otherwise queer socially constructed sex/gender boundaries". Our records move dates back to the first recorded instances of same-sex love and sexuality of ancient civilizations, involved the history of lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender people and cultures around the world. In a world before sexual preferences defined identity, men who desired other men were not thought of as members of a biologically-determined, distinctive subculture with a constant nature. Because men and women were not thought of as opposites, same-sex relationships were not considered to go against nature.

Physical Appearance:

In physical appearance of men and women is comparatively different. According to our men will appear both handsome and ugly vice versa women will appear beautiful and ugly. When it comes to apply for transgender or gay of course they also the same. They become to dominate to women in appearance more much possible as beautiful than women. Present days we unable to judge them whether are they woman or transgender or gay. Because they completely dress up as woman. The most interesting aspect of the festival is that men dress up as women and looking completely unrecognisable. It happens on “Chamayavilakku” festival which is celebrated at Devi temple in March every year in Kollam district in Kerala. If we look back history in The Mahabharata Arjuna cross-dressed as Brihannala and became a dance teacher. In the Agnyatvaas which they had to keep their identities secret to avoid detection, One of the first historical records of gay life in Buenos Aires were the criminal careers of several crossdressing swindlers, who were profiled by hygienists. There was a complex and visible culture of homosexuals and cross-dressers that extended in all the social classes of Buenos Aires during the late 19th and early 20th centuries. According to several testimonies, clandestine cross dressing balls were very popular among middle and upper class gay men in Buenos in the early-to-mid 20th century. Used by men and young boys dressing and playing both roles of male and female in theaters not only that cross dressing was become normal practice In medieval England.

Men who dress up as Woman:

Image tweeted by @Ananth_IRAS

Screen grab from video tweeted by @tweet_arvi

Comparison between Woman and Transgender in Appearance:

What are the rights of Transgender/Gay:

Of course every human being has their own rights to lead their life in this world. Though the nature provided the rights provided to them but the society can't. Because according to the psychology of human beings their thoughts are different on transgender/gay. They never treated to them as equal or never be think about them like they also as human being or treated as common man. These transgender/gay are always facing il-treatment in the society because

they belongs to third world though they are living in a unique world. Generally there are two worlds in a unique world they are 1. Men world 2. Women world. But unnaturally this transgender/ gay come forwarded as third world for their identity in this unique world. We know rights never be given immediately in free because for them must be fight. How women are fought for their rights to get.

Rights of Transgender/Gay:

1. Right of Residence
2. Right of Education
3. Right of Employment
4. Right of Health care
5. Recognition of Identity for a Transgender/Gay

Right of Residence:

In this world as human being each and every person have an equal right to lead their life or to live. According to the gender nature we are all have different capability at the same time men and women have different physical strength but this transgender/gay has both of strength but they struggle to lead their life in this society. This transgender/gays are struggled and still struggling to lead their life. Because the word become gay /transgender is only the big problem and their family members also can't digest and unable to accept as their family member. Why mean they belongs complete to another world and they become unnatural. On this reason they always are struggling to get their right. Very recently the Government of India has recognised and allotted a place to them in records and in applications under gender column as third gender.

Right of Education:

Now transgender/gays are become well educated in past they were not encouraged, a century ago how women were discriminated towards education like as the same this transgender/gay are discriminated. At present they are leading their life towards education by gaining good percentage and occupying good jobs like as Doctors, Teachers, Lawyers, IAS & IPS officers etc. If we observe them due to ill treatment of society they try to hide their gender without exposing and gaining education and uplifting their qualifications and their positions.

Right of Employment:

Very sure to lead our life or do you want to be lead life on earth food is must. So if we questioned our selves how to lead life the answer is must do work or job, without doing work

we can't. If you require something and want to fulfil then money is need. At the same time if you questioned how to get money then answer is job or work is must, whether it is government job, private job or any other job like labour. Whatever it is job is must. Now if we talk about mental condition of public at working place some of men are always try to abuse to women in different manner. The same conditions are faced by this transgender or gay. They can't get job opportunity immediately where ever they go mostly they harassment instead of getting job. So most of them choose begging as their income source. Here if observe them they are deviated in three parts to earn money. They are

1. As Beggars,
2. As Street performances for different occasions (marriages, shop openings, festival programs, etc),
3. As Sex workers.

Right of Health care:

As human being we are all given much priority to health care because health is wealth. We know that if we are healthy we can do anything we can go anywhere. When we are healthy then automatically healthy family relations and conditions are are good. According to this point transgender or gays will be treated or received well by their family members or their relatives or others. Due to this reason they will try to protect themselves without affect from any decease. Why mean if they are healthy they can earn money. Gays are respectable at their family up to they have income or earn money, otherwise they don't. According our concern knowledge all the human beings are treated as same.

Recognition of Identity for Transgender/Gay:

Transgender/Gays always struggled to their identity but society never recognized them. Because they are un-natural. Due to un-recognition and non co-operation and insults of their family and society some of them had stopped their life by suicide. Though society not identified them they create their own identity by their body language, way of talking and behaviour. Of course begging is one of the choice them to lead their life. When they go for begging into market or street they make sound with the claps that sounds in different way that sound become their identity along with that their vocal voice is also another identity to them. But another side of the mirror they fight against the law for their recognition because government never recognise them more over they are not eligible to get benefits which are issued by the government. Even they don't have proper address recognition to apply for job

or to receive something in postal/ courier. They don't have place in government forms. Finally they got their recognition after so many hurdles after acceptance of all countries worldwide recognised to provide the place as third gender.

Conclusion:

There are number of proofs were left by history for us regarding transgender or gays about their conditions. We can find depictions of same-sex sexual acts in temples like Khajuraho. In South Asia the Hijra (transgender or gay) are a caste of third gender or transgender people who live a feminine role. It's observable and understandable that sometimes family situations dominate them to become gay or to go far away to their family and lead life as an orphan why mean their family members not accept them as gay or transgender. So this reason all the transgender or gays are gather together and form a community and lead their life as a third world in this unique world. Based on an analysis of the United States of America 2018 Geneal Social Survey, One in five adults in the United States Know someone who uses non-binary pronouns other than he or she.

References:

1. Times of India: "[Gay rights groups hail bid to amend law](#)," 27/7/2002, accessed 15/5/ 2011
2. Vastayana (1929), Kama sutra Benaras: Jai Krishna das Haridas Gupta.ISBN:0192802704
3. Clare Sears (2008). "Electric Brilliancy: Cross-Dressing Law and Freak Show Displays in Nineteenth-Century San Francisco".
4. Altenburger, Roland (2005-01-01). "Is It Clothes that Make the Man? Cross-Dressing, Gender, and Sex in Pre-Twentieth-Century Zhu Yingtai Lore". Asian Folklore Studies.
5. Sears,Clare(2020). ArrestingDress. Duke University Press. ISBN 978-0-8223-7619-4.
6. Alison Bechdel, Fun Home: A Family Tragicomic, Houghton Mifflin, 2006